

Concordance Between Hysteroscopy, Ultrasound, and Pathological Findings in Perimenopausal Patients with Abnormal Uterine Bleeding

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ABSTRACT

OBJECTIVE: To determine the concordance between hysteroscopic, ultrasonographic, and pathological findings, estimating the sensitivity and specificity of hysteroscopy and ultrasound with the histopathological study in perimenopausal patients diagnosed with abnormal uterine bleeding during the period February 2024-November 2024 at the Veracruz High Specialty Hospital

MATERIAL AND METHODS: Records of perimenopausal patients with abnormal uterine bleeding who underwent an ultrasound and hysteroscopic evaluation at the Veracruz Regional High Specialty Hospital were reviewed. The Kappa test was applied for concordance of qualitative variables, the sensitivity and specificity of hysteroscopy and ultrasound with the histopathological study was estimated. Finally, the results will be grouped into pie charts and bar graphs.

RESULTS: we recorded data of 70 patients and we analiced a sensitivity of 0.93 (95%CI:) and specificity of 0.94 (95%CI:) were recorded for hysteroscopy, for ultrasonography a sensitivity of 0.93 (95%CI) and specificity of 0.93 (95%CI:). The concordance between histopathology and hysteroscopy was 0.8573724387 (KAPPA VALUE) (95%CI 1- 0.624)

CONCLUSIONS: Hysteroscopy in the diagnosis of the causes of abnormal uterine bleeding in perimenopausal women showed a remarkable concordance with the histopathological findings. The sensitivity and specificity values highlight hysteroscopy as a reliable and superior method compared to ultrasonography. The combination of both techniques can improve the diagnosis and management of these patients.

KEYWORDS: findings, hysteroscopic, ultrasonographic, anatomopathological, perimenopausal.

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BACKGROUND

Abnormal uterine bleeding is defined as a variation in the menstrual pattern that can be regular, duration, or frequent. It is the leading cause of gynecological consultation worldwide. The complete medical history and physical examination of the uterine cavity allow us to establish the diagnosis. ¹

In disorders of the uterine cavity and tubes, hysteroscopy is a procedure that has two purposes: diagnostic and therapeutic. This study is indicated in patients with suspected intracavitary uterine pathology as a cause of abnormal uterine bleeding. ² An abnormal endometrial ultrasonographic finding needs to be confirmed by hysteroscopic visualization with guided biopsy and consequent histological examination can increase

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diagnostic accuracy. The correlation between hysteroscopy and other non-invasive diagnostic methods has been studied. 3

METHODOLOGY

This was a descriptive and observational study, which included records of hysteroscopic procedures of patients with abnormal or postmenopausal uterine bleeding, attended at the High Specialty Hospital of Veracruz by a physician trained in minimally invasive gynecological endoscopic surgery in the months of February 2024 to November 2024. Women without a histopathological diagnosis were excluded.

The sample size was calculated using the formula to estimate a proportion, expecting a sensitivity of 95% (with a $Z \alpha = 3.8416$) a maximum allowed error of 5%, $p = 0.85$; $q = 0.15$; $d = 0.03$ a prevalence value in Mexico, known in the literature of 85%, the sample size is 72 patients.

The records of patients who underwent hysteroscopy due to abnormal uterine bleeding were reviewed, which was performed in an operating room, with vaginoscopy access technique according to Bettocchi's criteria. A rigid continuous flow hysteroscope with 2.9 mm Hopkins optics, 30-degree oblique forum vision, 4.9 mm sheath and 5 Fr operative canal was used as a means of distention. As a means of distention, a physiological solution administered with an Endomat (Karl Storz) pump at a pressure of 80 mmHg was used. with a volume of 200 ml per minute.

All procedures were performed at the Hysteroscopy Clinic, with the vaginoscopy access technique, according to Bettocchi's criteria (without speculum or neck forceps). 0.9% saline solution was administered as a means of distension, without anesthetic and on an outpatient basis.

Hysteroscopic findings were defined as the diagnostic impression based on observation of the surface of the uterine cavity prior to obtaining the endometrial biopsy documented by the physician specializing in minimally invasive gynecologic surgery in the clinical record. The final diagnosis was established by the doctors of the Histopathology service. Hysteroscopic and histopathological findings were classified into four diagnoses: endometrial polyp, endometrial hyperplasia with and without atypia, endometrial cancer, and submucosal leiomyoma.

The sensitivity and specificity of hysteroscopy were calculated. Patients were grouped into two categories: normal endometrium (healthy women) and abnormal endometrium (patients with endometrial polyp, submucosal fibroid, endometrial hyperplasia, endometrial cancer).

Sensitivity and specificity, positive and negative predictive value, 95% confidence interval (95%CI), Kappa value for concordance, and Pearson's correlation coefficient were calculated.

RESULTS

72 patient records were registered, patients without a pathological diagnosis were excluded; therefore, the final

analysis of the sample was 70 patients with a mean age of 46 (± 2) years.

Graph 1 shows the findings in perimenopausal women with abnormal uterine bleeding in hysteroscopy, including endometrial polyps (29%) and submucosal fibroids (21%), other diagnoses are presented in the corresponding graph. (Graph 1)

Graph 2 shows the most frequent findings in perimenopausal women with abnormal uterine bleeding by ultrasound, including endometrial hyperplasia 24 (57.14%) and submucosal fibroids 16 (38%), endometrial polyps 2 (4.5%). (Graph 2)

Of 24 patients diagnosed with endometrial hyperplasia by ultrasound, only 3 (12.5%) corresponded to hyperplasia without atypia, 5 (20%) to submucosal fibroids, and 13 (54%) to endometrial polyps.

Thus, 16 women with a diagnosis of submucosal fibroid by ultrasound corresponded to 14 (87.4%) by histopathology. Finally, 2 women with a diagnosis of endometrial polyp by usg corresponded to 1 (50%) by histopathology.

On the other hand, of 21 women diagnosed with submucosal fibroids by hysteroscopy, 18 (85%) reported submucosal fibroids by histopathology; they reported endometrial hyperplasia 3 (100%); of 15 patients diagnosed as endometrial polyp, 13 (86.6%) and finally of 3 patients who were found by hysteroscopy changes associated with malignancy, 3 (100%) were diagnosed with endometrioid adenocarcinoma.

A sensitivity of 0.93 (95%CI:) and specificity of 0.94 (95%CI:) were recorded for hysteroscopy. For the detection of the causes of abnormal uterine bleeding by hysteroscopy, a positive predictive value of 0.95 (95% CI: 0.95-0.98) and a negative 0.91% (95% CI: 0.75-0.83) were recorded. (Table 5) For ultrasonography, sensitivity and specificity of 0.93 (95% CI:) and specificity of 0.93 (95% CI) were recorded. For the detection of the causes of abnormal uterine bleeding by transvaginal ultrasonography, a positive predictive value of 0.95 (95% CI: 0.95-0.98) and a negative 0.90% (95% CI: 0.75-0.83) were recorded. (Table 5)

The correlation between histopathology and hysteroscopy was 0.992627285 (Pearson value) when the diagnosis is established as normal or abnormal endometrium. The concordance between histopathology and hysteroscopy was 0.8573724387 (kappa value) (95 CI 1-0.624) (Table 6)

DISCUSSION

The Federation of Gynecology and Obstetrics proposed two standardized classification systems for the etiologies of SUA symptoms: The Abnormal Uterine Bleeding Symptom Definition System (FIGO AUB SYSTEM 1). Where the definition of normal menstrual bleeding is given by 4 parameters: 1) Frequency: absent where there is no bleeding, infrequent <38 days, normal 24-38 days; frequent <24 days, 2) Duration; Normal <8 days or prolonged >8 days, 3)

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Regularity: a variation of 7-9 days, depending on age (18-25 years \leq 9 days; 26-41 years \leq 7 days; 42-45 years; 9 days); 4

Volume: little, normal or abundant. 4

Hysteroscopy is the standard for distinguishing between a type 2 and 3 leiomyoma with the determination based on the lowest filling pressure that allows visualization of the endometrial cavity. To distinguish between type 4 and type 5 leiomyomas, they must be based on the observation of the serosa distortion determined by ultrasound. Likewise, the location in the uterus and the volume must also be estimated.

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In postmenopausal patients with suspected endometrial polyps with suspected endometrial cancer, hysteroscopy with polypectomy has been suggested. Likewise, histopathological analysis of the polyp is mandatory due to the risk of malignancy. 6

To this day, transvaginal ultrasonography is the most widely used diagnostic tool, as it allows the clinician to study patients with dysmenorrhea, chronic pelvic pain and menometrorrhagia. In 2008, the International Endometrial Tumor Analysis (IETA) group proposed a consensus on the systematization of the examination technique that should be transvaginal. Each evaluation should begin with the identification of the bladder and cervix. The position of the uterus should be noted and measured, the uterus in a sagittal plane should be measured from the cervix to the fundus, in a transverse plane from horn to horn. The isonation angle between the uterus and the endometrium should be 90 degrees. 7

The following findings are characteristic of the presence of heterotopic endometrium and hypertrophic myometrial cells. At the ultrasonographic level, it is characterized by being an enlarged uterus with a myometrium with a mixed texture echo under two-dimensional sonography, with poorly defined lesions without shadows at the edges, anteroposterior myometrial asymmetry, mixed echogenicity translated into cysts, hyperechogenic islands, subendometrial lines with the presence of translesional Doppler flow, with thickened transformation zone, irregular and interrupted even in the absence of localized lesions. 8

Second-dimensional transvaginal ultrasound focuses on specific morphological patterns. Transvaginal ultrasonography allows the doctor to analyze the modifications of the attachment area. This area appears in the coronal plane as a hypochoic halo that surrounds the endometrium, in a thickness greater than >8 mm or inhomogeneous is highly likely. 9

Lesions suggestive of uterine myomatosis are described as well-defined hypoechogenic, with a Doppler pattern of a single circular vessel. The classification proposed by the International Federation of Gynecology and Obstetrics groups intracavitary fibroids into intracavitary type 0 pedunculated without intramural extension, type 1 that has an intramural extension. The free margin of the myometrium,

defined as the minimum thickness between the outer edge of the fibroid and the inner edge of the uterine serosa, is considered to be an important limiting factor for hysteroscopic resection of submucosal fibroids, suggesting a lower limit of 5 to 10 mm. This parameter is traditionally measured by transvaginal ultrasound (TVS) in the preoperative setting and is considered a static value, important since a measurement greater than this has been related to a higher risk of perforation and bleeding during the procedure. 10

Endometrial polyps are characterized at the ultrasonographic level by: hyperechogenic lesion, ovoid shape, regular margin, cystic areas, presence of single and central lesional vascularization. 3D ultrasonography has been used in the evaluation of the endometrium and compared with transvaginal 2D ultrasound, it has shown sensitivity of 100% and specificity of 99% with a positive predictive value of 99%. 11

According to the International Endometrial Tumor Association, the endometrial morphological features most likely to endometrial cancer were having a regular endometrial-myometrial junction (-23% difference; 95% CI, -27 to -18%), higher mean endometrial thickness ($+9\%$ difference; 95% CI, $+8$ to $+11\%$), and were more likely to have non-uniform echogenicity ($+7\%$ difference; 95% CI, $+1$ to $+13\%$), a multiple vessel and multifocal pattern ($+21\%$ difference; 95% CI, $+16$ to $+26\%$) and a moderate or high color score ($+22\%$ difference; 95% CI, $+18$ to $+27\%$). 12

Hysteroscopy offers a diagnostic option, which can be accurate and can offer treatment of intracavitary uterine pathology. The use of hysteroscopy in abnormal uterine bleeding replaces curettage, since it gives an accurate view obtained from the coordinated visualization of the cervical canal and endometrial cavity, with therapeutic results of the etiopathology causing abnormal uterine bleeding. 13

In a study carried out in women between 22 and 60 years of age who underwent diagnostic hysteroscopy, it was shown that 22% of women had abnormal uterine bleeding for 6 months, 33% had bleeding for 1 year. Of these patients, 37 had a thinning endometrium, with data suggestive of a proliferative endometrium, this sample was confirmed by histopathology in 32 patients, with a diagnostic accuracy of 86%. 14

In a study of patients with abnormal uterine bleeding, the incidence of focal intrauterine lesions was 52% for all ages and 31% for the group of postmenopausal patients, so three-quarters of patients with heavy bleeding have found focal pathology. 15

Hysteroscopy is a study that has shown greater sensitivity and specificity for endometrial biopsies, and that compared to dilation and curettage as well as transvaginal ultrasound, it exhibits greater sensitivity in intrauterine focal lesions. 16

Panoramic hysteroscopy has also been shown to be superior to 3D ultrasound and curettage in making an accurate

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diagnosis of uterine pathology, particularly in diagnosing polyps, especially with a size of less than 1 cm with better sensitivity ($p < 0.001$) without much difference in specificity ($p = 1.0$).¹⁷

One of the most common findings is endometrial cancer, which usually causes transvaginal bleeding. Hysteroscopy can not only visualize the appearance of endometrial cancer, but also demonstrate whether there is infiltration of the lower uterine segment and cervix. The concordance between hysteroscopic and histological findings is 89.9%.¹⁸

A hysteroscopy is considered negative, when criteria are found that indicate normality in the uterine cavity and in the endometrium, which are: an adequate visualization of the entire uterine cavity, uniform endometrial layer, homogeneous endometrium, without variations in endometrial thickness (early proliferative phase or in postmenopausal patients).¹⁹

A study that included the review of 250 hysteroscopy videos performed on patients where 152 of them had benign changes, 16 had an atypical endometrium and 18 with endometrial carcinoma. There are features that include protrusion, desquamation of the endometrium ($p = 0.001$, odds ratio [OR] 5.28), presence of atypical vessels ($p < 0.001$, OR 8.50) and yellowish-white lesions ($p = 0.011$, OR 1.37). They were significantly predictors of endometrial malignancy, with a sensitivity of 100% and specificity of 92%. They are highly predictive in the detection of endometrial malignancy.²⁰

There are high-risk hysteroscopic features such as endometrial thickening greater than 10 mm, polymorphic surface, irregular vascularization, grayish-white coloration, "cotton candy" lesions suggestive of necrotic endometrial tissue. The sensitivity for diagnosing endometrial lesions was 86.9% for mild lesions and 96% for severe lesions.^{21,22}

The visualization of the uterine cavity allows histological samples to be taken under visual control. The following aspects are generally indicative of this condition: a) irregular endometrium during the proliferative phase b) pronounced hypervascularization c) "strawberry" endometrial pattern d) intrauterine lesions of cystic appearance and fibrosis e) hemorrhagic cystic lesions of chocolate or blue appearance.²³

Endometrial polyps hysteroscopy offers insight into the endometrial cavity and a therapeutic option with removal of polyps at the same time. It has a sensitivity ranging from 58% to 99%, specificity from 87% to 100%, with a positive predictive value of 100% and a negative predictive value of 99%.²⁴

An additional critical function provided by hysteroscopy is to determine the extent of atypical hyperplasia and endometrial carcinoma into the endocervical canal. They are described by Francis and colleagues that based on the hysteroscopic diagnosis of hyperplasia one or more of the following findings: focal or diffuse, papillary or polypoid, endometrial thickening, evidence of glandular cysts.²⁵

A total of 5.3% of patients were diagnosed with endometrial adenocarcinoma and 62.5% with postmenopausal bleeding, with a high concordance between hysteroscopy and histological diagnosis in endometrial carcinoma, endometrial polyps, and normal endometrium.²⁶

An observational, descriptive, and cross-sectional study conducted in Tabasco in 2018, which evaluated 36 patients where the concordance between hysteroscopy and histopathology was studied in patients with abnormal uterine bleeding, showed a 90% agreement between hysteroscopy and low-risk endometrial hyperplasia to rule out structural pathology by identifying endometrial tissue with 88.2%.²⁷

A descriptive study that included 184 hysterectomy specimens from patients with abnormal uterine bleeding in the period from 2010 to 2011. Specimens were routinely processed and fixed with hematoxylin eosin and examined microscopically. They were found to be characterized by the presence of endometrial glands and stroma in myometrium.²⁸

Uterine fibroids are common findings in women with abnormal uterine bleeding. This bleeding is caused by the increase in size of the uterine cavity as it increases the surface area of the endometrium, vascular alterations in the endometrium and an obstructive effect of the uterine fibroid in the uterine vasculature causing venous endometrial ectasia to form which causes proximal congestion in the myometrium and endometrium.²⁹

Most endometrial polyps are composed of immature endometrium, which does not respond to hormonal stimulation. These polyps have the appearance of cystic hyperplasia, last all stages of the menstrual cycle and are not eliminated at the time of menstruation. Less commonly, endometrial polyps consist of functional endometrium undergoing cyclic histological changes.³⁰

A study that included 946 women that aimed to investigate the association of epidemiological and hysteroscopic parameters, with risk of developing malignancy within endometrial polyps. Endometrial carcinoma was found in 10 women (1.06%) and atypical hyperplasia was found in 11 women (1.16%).³¹

Abnormal uterine bleeding in perimenopausal patients is a common problem and responsible for high morbidity. During the year 2023 alone, approximately 1728 patients with abnormal uterine bleeding of intracavitary pathology were treated at the High Specialty Hospital of Veracruz.

This is a study that assesses the concordance of the results obtained, which has the strength of having personnel trained in minimally invasive surgery, to improve the concordance of the findings found in these studies. The results of this study provide information on the diagnosis and etiology of abnormal uterine bleeding (AUB) in perimenopausal women through the use of hysteroscopy and ultrasound, highlighting the high concordance between the histopathological findings and the diagnoses made by these techniques.

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In our sample of 71 patients, the mean age was 46 years, which is consistent with the literature suggesting that abnormal uterine bleeding is more frequent in the perimenopausal population. The most common findings observed on hysteroscopy were endometrial polyps (29%) and submucosal fibroids (21%). This highlights the importance of considering these conditions when evaluating women with abnormal uterine bleeding.

The correlation between diagnoses made by hysteroscopy and histopathological findings was remarkable with a Pearson coefficient of 0.99, indicating an extremely high concordance in the identification of normal or abnormal endometrium. The general agreement, reflected by the Kappa value (0.86), suggests that hysteroscopy is a very reliable tool for the diagnosis of intracavitary uterine pathologies.

In relation to sensitivity and specificity, both hysteroscopy and ultrasonography showed figures above 90%, with positive predictive values of 0.95 for both. These findings support the efficacy of hysteroscopy as a diagnostic method in the evaluation of abnormal uterine bleeding, being

comparable to ultrasonography, which is less invasive. However, hysteroscopy allows for direct evaluation and the possibility of simultaneous therapeutic interventions.

When analyzing the discordance in the diagnoses, we observed that of the 24 patients diagnosed with endometrial hyperplasia by ultrasound, only 3 corresponded to hyperplasia without atypia. This suggests that ultrasonography, while useful, may underestimate the complexity of the endometrium in this context, reinforcing the need for a complementary approach with hysteroscopy for a more accurate diagnosis.

Our results highlight the usefulness of hysteroscopy in the diagnosis of abnormal uterine bleeding in perimenopausia, showing a high agreement with histopathological findings. This suggests that hysteroscopy should be regarded as the gold standard in the evaluation of abnormal uterine bleeding, especially in cases where ultrasonography does not provide a clear diagnosis. Future research could focus on the cost-effectiveness of these diagnostic techniques to establish more efficient management protocols in clinical practice.

TABLES AND ANNEXES

Graph 1

Source: HAEV

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Graph 2

Source: HAEV

Table 5

Test	Value	CI -95%
Hysteroscopy		
Sensitivity	93%	95%
Specificity	94%	95%
Positive predictive value	95%	95-98%
Negative predictive value	91%	91%
Source: HRAEV		

Table 6

Test	Value	CI -95%
Transvaginal ultrasonography		
Sensitivity	93%	95%
Specificity	93%	95%
Positive predictive value	95%	95-98%
Negative predictive value	90%	75-83
Source: HRAEV		

Table 7

	Ultrasonography			Total
		Abnormal	Normal	
Ultrasonography	Abnormal	40	2	42
	Normal	3	26	29

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	Total	43	28	
Kappa Value	0.85%			
Pearson's coefficient	-100.00%			
Source: HRAEV				

Table 8

		Histopathology		
Hysteroscopy		Abnormal	Normal	Total
	Abnormal	37	2	39
	Normal	3	29	32
	Total	40	31	71
Kappa Value	0.857372439			
Pearson Sufficient	0.992627285			
Source: HRAEV				

CONCLUSIONS

This study confirms the high efficacy of hysteroscopy in diagnosing the causes of abnormal uterine bleeding in perimenopausal women, showing agreement with histopathological findings. The prevalence of endometrial polyps and submucosal fibroids as the most common etiologies underscores the importance of more extensive evaluation in this population.

The sensitivity and specificity values, as well as the high positive predictive values, highlight hysteroscopy as a reliable and superior method compared to ultrasonography. The combination of both techniques may improve the diagnosis and management of these patients, suggesting that hysteroscopy should be considered the gold standard in the evaluation of abnormal uterine bleeding.

These findings show the need for clinical protocols that integrate hysteroscopy as a fundamental tool in the investigation of UAS, contributing to a more precise and effective management of endometrial conditions in this population.

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